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Treatment of wastewater through vermifiltration technique using garden waste

Rajwinder Singh^{1*}, Arti Thanki², Ankita Thanki², Karanvir Singh Sohal³, Anmol Kaur⁴

¹Research Scholar, Department of Civil Engineering, DR BR Ambedkar National Institute of Technology, Jalandhar, Punjab, 144011 India

²Post Graduate Student, Department of Environmental Science and Engineering, Marwari University, Rajkot, Gujarat, 360003 India

³Post Graduate Student, Department of Civil Engineering, Guru Nanak Dev Engineering College Ludhiana, Punjab, 141006, India

⁴Graduate Student, Department of Science, Government college for girls, Ludhiana, Punjab, 141001, India

*Corresponding authors: Rajwinder Singh (rajwinderbirdi2@gmail.com)

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Introduction: The increase in urbanization and the population has increased the usage of water. Apart from the usage, a large amount of wastewater is generated from various sources such as residential, industrial, and public places (1). Therefore, there is a need for alternative sustainable techniques that could be used to treat that wastewater to meet the demand. Vermifiltration techniques are the technique which involves the usage of earthworms which are not only able to treat the wastewater but also helps to reduce the organic solid waste by converting it into nutrient-rich compost (2).

Methods: The present research work is focused on the vermifiltration process for quality assessment of wastewater collected from hostels kitchen of RIET, Phagwara, in the vermifilter using garden waste as padding media at fixed hydraulic loading rate (HLR) of 1.5 m³/m²/day. The bulk quantity of *Eisenia fetida* species of earthworm was used in the vermifilter. The performance of the vermifiltration process was examined by investigating the quality parameters such as pH, BOD (Biological Oxygen Demand), COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand), and TSS (Total Suspended Solids).

Results & Discussions: The treatment efficiency of vermifiltration process of BOD, COD, and TSS was observed to be above 92%, 85%, and 81%, respectively. The earthworm degrades the organic matter present in the wastewater into minute sized particles by their degradation activities (3).

Conclusions: The Vermifiltration technique has successfully led to treat the wastewater and makes it fit for irrigation purposes. The removal efficiency of the BOD, COD, and TSS at HLR of 1.5m³/m²/day through this facility is more than 85%, is more than any conventional treatment facility. Total suspended solids were not in the permissible limits; therefore, it is recommended to use any further post-treatment facility so as to make it possible for its proper application.

Keywords: Vermifiltration, Garden waste, Wastewater treatment

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